

Supporting Information for “Persistent coastal temperature biases in km-scale climate models due to unresolved oceanic tidal mixing”

Audrey Delpech¹, Anne-Marie Tréguier¹, Louis Marié¹, Rohit Ghosh²,

Malcolm J. Roberts³

¹Univ Brest, CNRS, Ifremer, IRD, Laboratoire d’Océanographie Physique et Spatiale, Plouzané, France

²Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Bremerhaven, Germany

³Met Office –Hadley Center, Exeter, UK

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1. Models and simulations used in the study.

Table S1. Coupled climate models used in this study. All models have been run with the HighResMIP protocol.

Institution	Model	Ocean Model	Ocean Resolution	Atmosphere Model	Atmosphere Resolution	Reference
Met Office (UK)	HadGEM-GC31-HH	NEMO-GO6.0	8 km	UM-GA7.1	50 km	M. J. Roberts et al. (2019)
NCAR (USA)	CESM1-CAM5-SE-HR	POP2	8 km	CAM5.2	25 km	Chang et al. (2020)
EC-Earth (EU)	EC-Earth3P-HR	NEMO	20 km	IFS	30 km	Haarsma et al. (2020)
BCC (China)	BCC-CSM2-HR	MOM4	20 km	BCC-AGCM3	40 km	Wu et al. (2020)
AWI (Germany)	AWI-IFS-FESOM-ER	FESOM	6 km	IFS	15 km	Ghosh et al. (2025)
CNRM (France)	CNRM-CM6-1-HR	NEMO	20 km	ARPEGE3.6	50 km	Voldoire et al. (2019)
CMCC (Italy)	CMCC-CM2-VHR4	NEMO3.6	20 km	CAM4	20 km	Scoccimarro et al. (2022)
ECMWF (Europe)	ECMWF-IFS-HR	NEMO3.4	20 km	IFS	30 km	C. D. Roberts et al. (2018)

2. Biases between observational datasets.

To ensure that the observed systematic biases in climate models (Figure 1) are not due to a defect in the observational product used as reference for the bias computation (ESA SST CCI), we cross-validated the product with another observational dataset, namely EN4, an objective analysis of monthly in-situ temperature at 1° from 1950 to present (Good et al., 2013). Figure S1 shows the difference between ESA SST CCI and EN4. The pattern shown in Figure S1 does not resemble, and cannot explain, the biases seen in the climate models (Figure 1).

Figure S1. Difference between EN4 and ESA SST CCI sea surface temperature averaged over 30 years (1985-2014).

3. Clustering analysis.

The method used for the clustering is the k-means (Kanungo et al., 2002). This is an iterative method separating N points in a given number n of cluster by minimizing the distance of each point to the mean (called the center) of each cluster. The Silhouette score allows for determining the ideal number of clusters (Shahapure & Nicholas, 2020). The score ranges between -1 and 1. 1 being the best (all clusters are far from each other) and -1 the worst, with values near 0 indicating overlapping clusters. The highest Silhouette scores are found for $n = 2$ in all 3 regions (Table S2).

Table S2. Silhouette score for the clustering analysis in the three example regions. n is the number of clusters.

	Northeastern American Shelf	Northwestern European Shelf	Yellow Sea
$n = 2$	0.54	0.55	0.49
$n = 3$	0.42	0.51	0.49
$n = 4$	0.38	0.46	0.45
$n = 5$	0.40	0.42	0.45
$n = 6$	0.39	0.39	0.43
$n = 7$	0.39	0.36	0.43

For each cluster, a correlation coefficient between S_h and the SST bias can be computed (Table S3). Pearson correlation coefficients range between -1 and 1. With -1 and 1 indicating perfectly linear relationships of correlation and anti-correlation, and values near 0 indicating no correlation. The correlation coefficients indicate an anti-correlation between the SST bias and S_h for low S_h values (Cluster 1) and no correlation for high S_h values (Cluster 2). The p-values indicate the probability of obtaining the given correlation coefficients with uncorrelated samples.

Table S3. For each cluster (see Figure 2 of the main document) and each example region, this table indicates: the cluster center, ρ : Pearson correlation coefficient between the Simpson-Hunter parameter S_h and the SST bias (b), \mathbf{p} : p-value under the null hypothesis of no correlation, interpreted as the probability to obtain the given correlation coefficient with uncorrelated samples.

		Northeastern American Shelf	Northwestern European Shelf	Yellow Sea
Cluster 1	center	(b=2.2°C, $S_h=4.1$)	(b=1.1°C, $S_h=3.2$)	(b=0.7°C, $S_h=2.9$)
	ρ	-0.2	-0.2	-0.4
	\mathbf{p}	1e-2	1e-11	1e-52
Cluster 2	center	(b=-0.7°C, $S_h=8.3$)	(b=0.1°C, $S_h=7.0$)	(b=0.2°C, $S_h=6.5$)
	ρ	0.01	0.02	-0.004
	\mathbf{p}	0.8	0.5	0.9

It is very low for Cluster 1 in each region, supporting the high probability of correlation between the two variables.

4. Multi-model mean Sea Surface Temperature biases in winter.

The Sea Surface Temperature (SST) bias in winter shows cold biases at the same locations as the summer warm biases (Figure 1). These biases are also collocated with the presence of tidal mixing fronts (Figure 2) and can be explained by the absence of tides and tidal mixing in climate models.

Figure S2. Same as Figure 1e, but for winter. Sea surface temperature (SST) bias on the continental shelves in winter averaged over 1985-2014 and across models for three example shelves: (a) the Northeastern American shelf, (b) the Northwestern European shelf, (c) the Yellow Sea. The black contours correspond to the isobaths (200 m, 500 m and 1000 m) and delineate the shelf break. The hatched areas correspond to biases $< \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

5. Effect of ocean resolution on Sea Surface Temperature biases in summer

The observed Sea Surface Temperature (SST) biases across the different HighResMIP models used in this study are also present in CMIP-like simulations and are relatively independent of model resolution. As an example, Figure S3 shows the SST bias in summer over the Northwestern European shelf for three different resolution of the HadGEM-GC31 model (Table S1). In the lower-resolution simulation (Figure S3c), coastal areas are less well represented due to a simplified coastline and land-sea mask, masking part of the biased area in the Channel Sea.

Figure S3. Sea Surface Temperature (SST) bias over the Northwestern European Shelf in summer averaged over 1985-2014 for the HadGEM-GC31 simulation (see Table 1) at three different oceanic resolution: (a) HadGEM-GC31-HH, ocean resolution ~ 8 km; (b) HadGEM-GC31-MM, ocean resolution ~ 25 km; (c) HadGEM-GC31-LL, ocean resolution ~ 100 km (CMIP-like simulation). All regridded to a common 0.25° grid.

6. Bias details for each model

The Sea Surface Temperature (SST) biases are relatively robust from one model to another. While Figure 1 only shows a sub-sampled number of models, Figure S4 show the bias in the 3 regions for all the models listed in Table S1.

Figure S4. Sea surface temperature (SST) bias on the continental shelves in summer averaged over 1985-2014 for the different models: (a) HadGEM-GC31-HH (Met Office, UK); (b) CESM1-CAM5-SE-HR (NCAR, USA); (c) EC-Earth3P-HR (EC-Earth Consortium, EU); (d) BCC-CSM2-HR (BCC, China); (e) AWI-EERIE-IFS-FESOM (AWI, Germany); (f) CNRM-CM6-1-HR (CNRM, France); (g) CMCC-CM2-VHR4 (CMCC, Italy); (h) ECMWF-IFS-HR (ECMWF, EU) and in three different regions: Northeastern American Shelf (left), Northwestern European Shelf (middle), Yellow Sea (right). The hatches correspond to biases $< \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. The colorbar is the same as for Figure 1.

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